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THE ARDUOUS CHALLENGE OF REALIZING SUSTAINABLE SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY: A CASE STUDY OF MFIs

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ABSTRACT

Microfinance Institutions (MFIs) established for the purpose of bringing sustainable development to the poor are now themselves struggling with the perils of their own sustainability. The success or failure of an enterprise depends upon its ethical business performance and MFIs are not an exception to this rule. The Microfinance crisis in Andhra Pradesh was an eye-opener for Indian MFIs making them ask very pertinent questions about their existence, sustainability and functionality of operations. The already existing literature on this subject has highlighted several issues contributing to the Microfinance crisis. This study is an endeavor to evaluate the indicators that negatively impact MFIs' sustainability. In some cases, borrowers of the funds provided by MFIs improperly use the finance made available to them in non-economic, household and personal activities that ultimately make them defaulters for non-repayment of loan. Cumulatively, this results in MFIs suffering significant losses due to the formation of bad debts and Non-Performing Assets (NPAs) thus making them resort to coercive means and malpractices for loan recoveries. This dissuades many from lending at all to the impoverished and thus with no means for economic upliftment, the poor remain poor. The MFIs also exercise discretion while choosing the category of their borrowers. Through this analytical paper, the basic causal relations are diagnosed and focus is set on sustainable development of MFIs to enable them to act as catalysts for achieving poverty alleviation.

Keywords: Microfinance Institutions (MFIs), Sustainability, Ethical issues, Social Performance, Profitability, Andhra Pradesh crisis.

INTRODUCTION

Microfinance today has become one of the most debated and documented but still much confused buzzword in banking, finance and policymaking. Simplistically, it can be termed as 'banking for the poor'. It is claimed to be a powerful tool which can be used effectively to address poverty alleviation, empower the socially marginalized poor and strengthen the social fabric. Microfinance is not just about lending money. A lot of other activities are also attached with it such as providing training to the borrowers, opening Savings or Recurring Deposit Accounts, improving Human Development Index (HDI), etc.

In 1959, Akhter Hameed Khan as the founder of Pakistan (now Bangladesh) Academy for Rural Development introduced the revolutionary idea of micro-credit (microfinance) thereby opening a new door for millions of destitute and underprivileged people. His Comilla Cooperative Pilot Project is considered a model of micro-credit and rural development initiatives in developing countries. In 1971, Al Whittaker and David Bussau established Opportunity International, which provides opportunities for people in chronic poverty to transform their lives by creating jobs, stimulating small businesses, and strengthening communities. Small loans ranging from \$ 25 to \$ 500 helped poor families lift themselves out of poverty with dignity. In 1973, ACCION International, focused on providing economic opportunities to poor people instead of working on construction/infrastructure projects in order to create lasting improvements in the lives of those they were helping. In 1976, Muhammad Yunus founded the Grameen Bank (GB) to make loans to poor Bangladeshis which revolutionized the world of micro financing and gave it international recognition.

The concept of sustainability is a little difficult to define as it has different connotations under different contexts. In the financial context, sustainability is deemed to refer to the financial and economic viability of the operations of the institution. A financial institution must be sustainable for it to continue and expand its activities. This is particularly true for MFIs where financial sustainability and sufficient profits are imperative to support ongoing operations and fulfil fiduciary obligations. Littlefield (2004) claims, "If you're going to provide financial services permanently to people, they've got to be sustainable, and that means charging interest rates that cover your costs." But many argue that increased focus on banking activities like interest, makes an MFI lose focus of its primary aim of poverty alleviation and economic development. There are numerous MFIs who are involved in making "microcredit" available to businesses and small enterprises thereby amounting to a high degree of Non-Performing Assets (NPAs) which often leads to financial unavailability of these MFIs.

The sustainability quotient of MFIs sometimes lead them to resort to predatory lending terms on borrowers. This results into a splintering of the business ethics by the MFIs, thus becoming the root cause for microfinance's disastrous crisis in countries like Nicaragua, Morocco, Bosnia and Herzegovina (BiH) and Pakistan. The problem being - Concentrated market competition and multiple borrowing, overstretched MFI systems and controls, and erosion of MFI lending discipline (Focus Note 61, Feb 2010, CGAP). Bolivia witnessed a microfinance crisis during 1999-2001 due to severe competition among existing microfinance troupes and consumer lenders which lead to over-indebtedness of clients (Constantinou and Ashta, 2011). Even a country like India could not escape the shackles of microfinance crisis and saw a similar one in Andhra Pradesh in early October 2010 which threatened the survival and sustainability of operations of MFIs in India. The negative impact of the crisis was felt by every state of India and affected its loan disbursement procedures for the fear of potential insolvency of the clients. A lot of MFIs in Andhra Pradesh entered into a fierce competition amongst themselves in hopes of growing their portfolio to maximize their profits to attain and preserve sustainability. Undeniably the principle of sustainability is the key that separates for-profit private MFIs from non-profit MFIs and Self-Help Groups (SHGs). Both NGO-based MFIs and SHGs rely on incessant sponsorship from national and international private and state donors.

LITERATURE SURVEY

According to Frances Sinha (2006), a good governance is expected when accountability, fairness, responsibility and transparency are practiced. The onus is on the board of directors to ensure effective governance and ethics. For MFIs, the board acts on behalf of all the stakeholders including the management, staff, investors, donors and clients. It is the duty of the board to separate the events of corporate social responsibility from social performance management. The consistency between the two important areas – social and financial changes due to the desire for attaining financial sustainability, commercialization and expectation of profit through capital returns thereby jeopardizing the primary motive behind the setting up of MFIs.

Since the private social investors are attracted towards investing in microfinance it should be made mandatory for MFIs to cultivate the measurements for the simultaneous carrying out of financial and social objectives, and for reporting on it in a manner which can qualify the test of external auditing on both accounts. This can also help to develop an understanding of the probable trade-offs between economic and social returns on investment as suggested by Manfred Zeller et al. (2003).

Tricia D. Olsen (2013) elaborated that the ethical value with microfinance are doubted today due to the aggressive lending practices, exorbitant interest rates, and underwhelming development outcomes. The ethical issues met by the MFIs are a function of how the governing body outlines the prominence of specific stakeholders. A typology of microfinance is created from the primary study conducted in Brazil, India, and Mexico delivering a further platform to recognize and state the aspects that have contributed to MFI's achievements and deficiencies. The typology that Indian MFIs fall under is the 'Bottom of the Pyramid(BOP) Approach' to microfinance, that is; to reach out to the poorest of the poor. The major demerit of this model is that the vastly competitive nature of the BOP method combined with the introduction of private equity investment in microfinance adds to over indebtedness, extortionate interest rates, and

excessively coercive collection methods. This holds true because majority of MFIs in India are set up as a revenue generation plot and initiatives led by family and friends as board of directors. Under the BOP model, MFIs also have the option to elude loaning to the impoverished.

Franke et al. (2011) explained that the immense rise of the MFIs in Andhra Pradesh was driven by just one factor - maximization of profit in every way possible. Additional outlets were opened and attempts were made to rope in as many deprived as they could. The officials facilitated loan to the less creditworthy debtors in the process of increasing the number of borrowers in order to boost the existing returns. These for-profit MFIs savoring rapid growth failed to diagnose and evaluate the risks attached with such accomplishments and neglected to raise the quality of their internal control, thus weakening the accounting and reporting structure. The officials engaged in advancing loan to the borrowers were authorized by the board to advance huge funds which led to large scale embezzlement by the officers. This marked the end of ethical practices by those MFIs. The rapid spreading out of MFIs in Andhra Pradesh principally for financial gain produced a strong competition among the MFIs. Hence, there was a major shift by some of the MFIs from social intent to an entire profit maximizing entity. Other Microfinance establishments such as SHGs and NGO-based MFIs asserted that the effectiveness of Microfinance was tumbled down by the profit enthused MFIs. The board together with the management control system of the MFIs were negligent in calculating the estimated risk and lacked in producing fair disclosure of information thereby causing a breakdown in the sustainability of the MFIs. Also a few other political factors added to the already existing aggravation.

(Kaur and Dey(2013) revealed that MFIs resorted to unethical means to retrieve the lent sum, resulted into 54 suicides by the defaulters, accusation of multiple borrowing and incriminating extravagant interest rates compelled the Andhra Pradesh (AP) Government to declare an ordinance in October 2010, which came in as a rescue to the debtors who were unable to repay the loan. The enactment of this ordinance led to an end to the gruesome practice followed by the MFIs. The microfinance crisis in AP has tarnished the microfinance industry as a whole. The banks, financial institutions and other donors were unwilling to provide loans to MFIs for the insecurity and risk involved with it. Thus, profitability and sustainability of MFIs were affected the most due to liquidity crunch.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To check the relationship between ethical performance and sustainability of MFIs.
2. To examine the sustainability of for-profit and Non-profit MFIs both.
3. To identify the causes leading to repayment crisis of MFIs with special focus on Andhra Pradesh crisis.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

To undertake this study, information is procured from the available Annual Reports together with journals, published seminar papers, internet, reflexive journals, etc. for the use of secondary data.

PROFITS FOR SUSTAINABILITY – ETHICAL OR INNUENDO?

A notable quote by Aristotle - “To give away money is an easy matter and in any man’s power. But to decide to whom to give it, and how large, and when, and for what purpose and how, is neither in every man’s power nor an easy matter.”

It is a well-known fact that extending loans to micro-entrepreneurs has a fairly attractive platform to make profits and growth. In some areas, like Asia, Africa and Latin America the profitability of MFIs is already embraced by greater competition in the industry (Lascelles, 2008). To sustain the double bottom line objectives, stakeholders of MFI ought to be administered by social obligation. Profit driven stakeholders will transform the industry into an increasing price and rushing for growth institution, ignoring the importance to the practices of the clients (Tadele, 2014). On the contrary, Cull et al. (2009) supported that grossing profits do not indicate being a ‘for profit’ body. Non-profit MFIs may make positive profits that are not circulated among investors/stakeholders but are instead pumped back into the

institutions' accounts for their smooth services to the clients. So to speak, the reward of profit, economists assumed, encourages all entrepreneurs and officials which result in effective decision making by private firms (Weisbrod, 1998). MFIs are capable of efficiently carrying out both the tasks of addressing poverty alleviation while supporting their own sustainability. "Rather than concentrating on an MFI's 'commercialization,' attention should be focused on how to reduce costs per client" (Mersland & Strøm, 2010).

Sustainability is attained when an MFI is able to meet all of its expenses. In fact, light needs to be thrown back on how one might bring about non-profit competition among efficient MFIs in order to reduce costs (both operating and financial) and lower operative interest rates thereby achieving an increase in profitability. It is observed that competition among MFIs raises the burden to inflate the competitive and marketable interest rates. Therefore, cost reduction should be the ultimate aim of MFIs which will lead interest rates to bow down as well. For instance, Economist (2008) reflects the case of for-profit MFI Compartamos in Mexico that went public in 2007 as a microfinance bank. Compartamos Banco listed shares of over US\$1 billion and netted humongous profits by charging their clients interest rates of at least 79 percent per year. It was called down as loan sharks for their exorbitant rates. However, this is not a classic case of deceit by the microfinance industry but more of an issue on unethical practice. The inherent message is that emphasis on profits drift MFIs away from their mission and the commitment to productively lend to the needy purposely slipping off microfinance services or elevating interest rates to answer the demands of greater profitability. What is necessary for sustenance of MFIs is their performance and behavior and the understanding of whether particular decisions taken by them are in positively correlated to their organizational goals so that the revenue generated from the loans and other assets are utilized well to meet the overall cost of the organisation and the surplus profit be ploughed back into the company for further activities (World Development Vol. 41, 2013).

ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

Microfinance has grown rapidly, from a simple anti-poverty program into a major player in the financial industry. And this growth has led to a deviation from its original goals and a general conflict between its ideals. Many microfinance institutions sacrifice welfare at the altar of financial gains. Some are known to viciously chase down creditors and use nefarious means to make good on their loans. Poor people are forced to take loans to repay their old loans and thus tend to fall into a vicious cycle of loans and interest. This access to easy money with low interest has further spoilt the economic endeavors of people and a significant amount of money is spent on non-economic purposes. The crisis that took place in Andhra Pradesh was not one of its kind in microfinance worldwide. The Indian MFIs ignored the past cases of Microfinance repayment crisis in other countries like Bolivia, Latin America, etc. and repeated the same mistakes. Some view microfinance primarily as an investment opportunity, with reducing poverty as either a secondary goal or not really a goal at all. This is a major deviation from the initial years of the introduction of the concept where it was purely used as a method for social and economic development.

From a scrutiny of the performance of MFIs in India from M-CRIL Microfinance Review 2012 showing CRILEX for a nine year period (March 31, 2003 to March 31, 2012), it is evident that MFIs had a wonderful growth for a period of seven years till March 2010 wherein CRILEX had stretched up to a level of 7,474 (with March 2003=100), as of 4,589 in the preceding year entering a composite growth of 63% in the fiscal year April 2009 to March 2010 without interrupting the trend of the preceding years. There is a kink on the graph from March 2010 to March 2011 due to the Andhra Pradesh crisis where microfinance industry was predicted to reach its highest at 9000. Therefore, the following year (March 31, 2011) was a slowdown of 7.3% composite growth and the index recorded at 8,005 and a downward trend in March 2012 was seen where CRILEX assessed to have dropped below 6000 by end of September 2012 indicating a fall over 33% from its maximum point in the microfinance services of the leading Indian MFIs.

Source: M-CRIL Microfinance Review 2012

Note: CRILEX is a composite index of the growth of Indian MFIs and uses information on the number of borrowers as well as the size of loan portfolio of the 24 leading MFIs (each with more than 1,00,000 active client accounts) in the country. It adjusts the client numbers by the most conservative estimations for multiple lending by M-CRIL experts.

The evidence that microfinance does bring people out of poverty is mixed. Some say it has helped millions of poor people, mostly women. Others say it hasn't and is, in fact, a debt trap for the poor. Microfinance is a multi-headed creature with no agreed-upon strategy or approach. There is no consensus on how to measure 'social performance'. There is no way in which donors can differentiate between a programme focused on poverty reduction from one focused on maximizing profit. Multiple borrowing is an extremely common problem among rural poor, with an estimated 84% of households having two or more loans from any source (D Johnson, 2010). Also, cases of multiple borrowing appear to be driven by an inability to obtain sufficient credit from a single source poses another issue. This significantly raises the interest component on the loans and defeats the primary purpose of MFIs of making low interest credit available to the economically challenged sections of the society.

Limitation faced by MFIs - Studies note that loans are used for productive and non-productive uses, including consumption. The figure below highlights how households from Kadapa and Visakhapatnam districts in Andhra Pradesh had taken more than one loan within two successive months for using their loan money. The data on loan usage reveals that 27% of loans were used for household consumption. An analysis of the usage at the household level reveals that 47% of the respondents mentioned household consumption as one of the reasons for them to borrow. This was followed by Health at 22% claiming that it was one of the reasons to borrow, followed by purchasing agricultural machinery or inputs (16%). This reveals that a significant amount of the micro credit made available to the poor is used for non-economic purposes which has resulted in the failure of the objectives of the MFI sector.

Usage of Loan money within two successive months

Source : CMF Focus Note (IFMR Lead)

CONCLUSION

The study was an attempt to add to the understanding of the relationship between performance and sustainability of MFIs. The study through its wide array of literature found that sustainability is directly dependent on performance of socially responsible MFIs. Negligent performance shown by MFIs in the form of careless governance or obtaining profit brings in a corrupt name for itself destroying its identity forever. As a result many MFIs had to be shut down in India. This marks the end of an MFI’s sustainable operations too. This study is envisioned to be a useful contribution to the researchers and policy makers in their ability to realize that high profitability of an MFI is not directly related to sustainability. In fact earning revenues by MFIs proportionate to cover overall costs, expenses and interest payments is just sufficient to meet the standards of sustainability. This relationship helps to differentiate between for-profit and non-profit MFIs. Significant factors are observed through this study that highlight the causes and consequences of the Andhra Pradesh crisis so that such disasters at least can be prevented from occurring in other countries especially in developing countries like Myanmar, Africa, Bangladesh, etc.

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